

Angular Momentum, Quantum Gravity, and Megalithic Sites

By

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Abstract

It may be that the problem of reconciling gravity with quantum mechanics is an abstract problem, one that may have already been encountered by our ancient ancestors who erected stone observatories like Stonehenge (megalithic sites) and it may be that they found the solution in the megalithic yard, a unit of measurement for aligning stones. Presented here is the author's earlier theory that provides a wave solution to the Earth/Moon/Sun system that is solved with a characteristic time of one second that is shown to solve also the atom's proton. As such, it is suggested we can look at the Solar System, which is gravitational, to solve the quantum realm and provide a grand unified theory. It is suggested we might be able to help find such a solution by looking at ancient megalithic sites.

Data Used In This Paper

$$m_p: 1.67262 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg (Proton Mass)}$$

$$h: 6.62607 \times 10^{-34} \text{ J} \cdot \text{s (Planck Constant)}$$

$$r_p: 0.833 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m (Proton Radius)}$$

$$G: 6.67408 \times 10^{-11} \text{ N} \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{kg}^2} \text{ (Gravitational Constant)}$$

$$c : 299,792,458 \text{ m/s (light speed)}$$

$$\alpha: 1/137 \text{ (Fine Structure Constant)}$$

$$q_p = q_e = 1.6022 \text{ E} - 19 \text{ coulombs}$$

$$k_e = 8.988 \text{ E} 9 \frac{\text{Nm}^2}{\text{C}^2}$$

Earth day=(24)(60)(60)=86,400 seconds. Using the Moon's orbital velocity at aphelion, and Earth's orbital velocity at perihelion we have:

$$KE_{moon} = \frac{1}{2} (7.347673 \text{ E} 22 \text{ kg}) (966 \text{ m/s})^2 = 3.428 \text{ E} 28 \text{ J}$$

$$KE_{earth} = \frac{1}{2} (5.972 \text{ E} 24 \text{ kg}) (30,290 \text{ m/s})^2 = 2.7396 \text{ E} 33 \text{ J}$$

Introduction One can speak of the structure of the long term structure of the solar system. The whole object of developing a theory for the way planetary systems form is that they meet the following criterion: They predict the Titius-Bode rule for the distribution of the planets; the distribution gives the planetary orbital periods from Newton's Universal Law of Gravitation. The distribution of the planets is chiefly predicted by three factors: The inward forces of gravity from the parent star, the outward pressure gradient from the stellar production of radiation, and the outward inertial forces as a cloud collapses into a flat disc around the central star. These forces separate the flat disc into rings, agglomerations of material, each ring from which a different planet forms at its central distance from the star (they have widths). In a theory of planetary formation from a primordial disc, it should predict the Titius-Bode rule for the distribution of planets today, which was the distribution of the rings from which the planets formed.

Also, the Earth has been in the habitable zone since 4 billion years ago when it was at 0.9 AU. Today it is at 1AU, and that habitable zone can continue to 1.2 AU. So we can speak of this distance to the Earth over much time. The Earth and Sun formed about 4.6 billion years ago. As the Sun very slowly loses mass over millions of years as it burns fuel doing fusion, the Earth slips microscopically further out in its orbit over long periods of time. The Earth orbit increases by about 0.015 meters per year. The Sun only loses 0.00007% of its mass annually. The Earth is at 1AU=1.496E11m. We have $0.015\text{m}/1.496\text{E}11\text{m}/\text{AU}=1.00267\text{E}-13\text{AU}$. So,

$$(1.00267\text{E} - 13\text{AU}/\text{year})(1\text{E}9\text{years}) = 0.0001\text{AU}$$

The Earth will only move out one ten thousandth of an AU in a billion years. Anatomically modern humans have only been around for about three hundred thousand years. Civilization began only about six thousand years ago.

The unit of a second becomes important in my theory. We got the second from the rotation period of the Earth at the time the moon came to perfectly eclipse the Sun. The Moon slows the Earth rotation and this in turn expands the Moon's orbit, so it is getting larger, the Earth loses energy to the Moon. The Earth day gets longer by 0.0067 hours per million years, and the Moon's orbit gets 3.78 cm larger per year.

That is as the Earth's day gets longer and the lunar orbit grows larger, we got the second at the time that the Earth day was what it is during the epoch when the Moon perfectly eclipses the Sun, 24 hours.

The near perfect eclipse is a mystery in the sense that it came to happen when anatomically modern humans arrived on the scene, even before that, perhaps around Homo Erectus and the beginning of the Stone Age. The Earth day was 18 hours long, long before that, 1.4 billion years ago. Homo Erectus is around two to three million years ago.

Angular Momentum, Quantum Gravity, And Ancient Megalithic Sites

At the heart of a grand unified field theory which would bridge general relativity with quantum mechanics, is the concept of angular momentum; Planck's constant, which is at the core of quantum mechanics, has units of angular momentum. This is an active area in theoretical physics for developing a theory for quantum gravity. This is because gravity is an inverse square law and moment of inertia has a squared dependence, which suggests that spacetime curvature (gravity) may be coupled to quantum spin.

I find it possible that this basic problem may be encoded in ancient megalithic structures, like Stonehenge, which are ancient observatories. They are stones placed with alignments for the Moon and the Sun due to the Earth's rotation and orbit around the Sun. I find I can quite simply explain why I believe in this connection of quantum gravity to ancient stone monuments. The rotational velocity of the Earth at its equator which determines how far things on the Earth surface travel over time, is:

$$1. \quad v_{rot} = (2\pi R_e)(f_e)$$

Where R_e is the Earth's radius and f_e is its rotational frequency. We can write this

$$2. \quad v_{rot} = \frac{M_e R_e}{M_e R_e} (2\pi R_e)(f_e)$$

$$3. \quad v_{rot} = \frac{(4/5)\pi M_e F_e R_e^2}{M_e R_e} \cdot \frac{60}{24}$$

Because

$$4. \quad \frac{4}{5} \cdot \frac{60}{24} = 2$$

This means that

$$5. \quad v_{rot} = \frac{L_{earth}}{M_e R_e} \cdot \frac{60}{24}$$

because the rotational angular momentum of the Earth is given by

$$6. \quad L_{earth} = (4/5)\pi M_e F_e R_e^2$$

Which is derived from the moment of inertia, I :

$$7. \quad I = \frac{2}{5} M R^2$$

$$8. \quad L = I\omega$$

$$9. \quad \omega = 2\pi f$$

This is interesting in equation 5 having the ratio 60/24 because it suggests we use the ancient Sumerian method of dividing-up the rotation of the Earth to measure time, and this method gives us the unit of a second we have today which I will show is the characteristic time of a wave solution for the solar system and the atom's proton. Our base unit of time that we have today came from the ancient Sumerians having divided the Earth's rotation period (an earth day) into 24 units that we today call hours. The ancient Babylonians further used the the ancient Sumerian's system of base 60 counting to divide the hour into 60 minutes, and each minute into 60 seconds, giving us the duration of our base unit of a second that we have today. It is further interesting that

$$10. \quad \frac{60}{24} = \frac{5}{2} = 2.5$$

This is important because 2.5 megalithic yards (MY) are recurrent throughout Stonehenge and other megalithic sites in Europe. The megalithic yard is a proposed ancient unit of measurement, approximately 0.829 meters that was suggested by the Scottish engineer Alexander Thom in the 1960's. He derived it from his survey of Neolithic stone circles, standing stones, and other megalithic structures in Britain and Brittany. Also, 2.5 occurs in the moment of inertia, I , which is the rotational analog to linear mass. For a solid sphere it is equation 7:

$$I = \frac{2}{5}MR^2$$

And it is the reason that the 2 in 4/5 commutes to the π giving $2\pi R_e$ the circumference of the Earth in the above equations 2 and 3 for the velocity at the surface of the Earth equator leaving 2/5 which is the 24/60 of the Sumerian counting that gave us a second. This connects ancient megalithic sites (2.5 MY) to the idea that there is a connection between gravity

$$11. \quad F \propto \frac{1}{r^2}$$

and rotational resistance

$$12. \quad I \propto r^2$$

I have found that one second is the characteristic time that describes the solar system and proton in common in a wave solution for the the Earth/Moon/Sun system. Let's go into that a little bit, then pick this up again...

The Theory

We begin with the characteristic time for our solution is one second and is given by the mass of the moon, M_m , cubed:

$$13. \quad \frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 1second$$

Yes, it does happen to be one second, our base unit of time we have today, ultimately given to us by the ancient Sumerians when they invented mathematics thousands of years ago. This becomes important, as we will see. The other extraordinary thing we find is that the Planck-type constant \hbar_{\odot} for our solar system

is given by the kinetic energy of the Earth, the third planet where life is extraordinarily abundant, multiplied by one second.

$$14. \quad \hbar_{\odot} = (1second)KE_e$$

We find our equations hold so well when the Earth day is about what it is today (24 hours long) giving a characteristic time of close to one second in terms of the kinetic energy of the Moon and the Earth:

$$15. \quad \frac{KE_m}{KE_e}(EarthDay) = 1.1 - 1.3seconds$$

I also find that this characteristic time of one second is characteristic of the proton, the most fundamental unit that makes up matter, predicting its radius:

$$16. \quad \left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

$$17. \quad \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1second$$

Where r_p and m_p are the radius and mass of a proton. Equating these two gives about the radius of a proton:

$$18. \quad r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c m_p}$$

This is very close to the value upon which the proton radius converged historically by two independent methods which was 0.877E-15m. The result from our theory is

$$19. \quad r_p = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{6.62607E - 34}{(299,792,458)(1.67262E - 27)} = 0.88094E - 15m$$

The 0.877fm was challenged in 2010 by a third experiment making it 4% smaller and was 0.842E-15m. I suggest it may be that the radius of a proton is actually

$$20. \quad r_p = \phi \cdot \frac{h}{c m_p} = 0.816632E - 15m$$

utilizing an optimization characteristic of the golden ratio, as Nature often does, where $\phi = 0.618$ is the golden ratio. The most recent value is 0.833E-15m. In this case we say

$$21. \quad \left(\sqrt{\phi \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1second$$

Where equation 17

$$\left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1 \text{second}$$

is a little over a second, and 21

$$\left(\sqrt{\phi \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1 \text{second}$$

is a little under a second. The proton doesn't have a precise size, but is fuzzy like a cloud of subatomic particles. It can have a functional radius depending on the Nature of the problem, which determines the definition of what its radius is.

The ancient Sumerians were responsible for giving us the unit of a second because they divided the earth's rotation period, its day, into 24 hours, and the ancient Babylonians divided each hour into 60 minutes, and each minute into 60 seconds from the ancient Sumerians base 60 mathematics. Perhaps the most exciting equation in our theory is:

$$22. \quad \frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60$$

Where L_{earth} is the rotational angular momentum of the Earth. This specifies not only that the rotation period of the Earth is best measured by dividing the day into 24 units and 60 units, but that such an optimization includes the mass and radius of the Earth. Another exciting equation in our theory is that during the time in the Earth's history when the day is about 24 hours which specifies close to a second from the kinetic energies of the Earth and Moon, the Moon perfectly eclipsing the Sun as seen from the Earth, holds:

$$23. \quad \frac{r_{planet}}{r_{moon}} = \frac{R_{star}}{R_{moon}}$$

r_{planet} is the orbital radius of the Earth, r_{moon} is the orbital radius of the Moon, R_{star} is the radius of the Sun, and R_{moon} is the radius of the Moon. The Moon makes life so successful on Earth because it holds the Earth at its inclination to its orbit around the Sun, preventing temperature extremes and allowing for the seasons.

The Schrödinger Wave Equation must be solved to determine the energies and orbitals of the electron in the hydrogen atom. In spherical coordinates it is

$$24. \quad -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left[\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin \theta \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \phi^2} \right] \psi + V(r)\psi = E\psi$$

It has the solutions

$$25. \quad E_n = -\frac{Z^2(k_e e^2)^2 m_e}{2\hbar^2 n^2}$$

$$26. \quad r_n = \frac{n^2 \hbar^2}{Z k_e e^2 m_e}$$

I find the solutions are for the Earth orbiting the Sun are:

$$27. \quad KE_e = \sqrt{n} \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{G^2 M_e^2 M_m^3}{2\hbar_\odot^2}$$

$$28. \quad r_n = \frac{2\hbar_\odot^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{R_\odot}{R_m} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$$

R_\odot is the solar radius, R_m that of the Moon. For Earth $n = 3$, third planet. Because these have accuracies close to 100% accurate we know that our equation for the solar system Planck constant is correct, equation 14:

$$\hbar_\odot = (1\text{second})KE_e$$

The Value of the Solar System Planck Constant

Let us now compute the value of \hbar_\odot and show that the units work...

$$\hbar_\odot = (hC)KE_e$$

$$hC = 1\text{second}$$

Where from equation 17

$$C = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2 c} \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{G m_p^3}}$$

Where r_p is the radius of a proton, m_p is the mass of a proton, c is the speed of light, and α is the fine structure constant. We found this gives the characteristic time of one second in terms of a proton. We guess the planetary scale is connected to the proton scale because the planets formed from the protoplanetary disc and it is made of different combinations of protons. We derive the value of our solar Planck constant:

$$C = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha^2 c} \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{2\pi r_p}{G m_p^3}} =$$

$$\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{18769}{299792458} \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{2\pi(0.833E - 15)}{(6.67408E - 11)(1.67262E - 27)^3}}$$

$$=1.55976565E33$$

$$= \frac{s}{m} \sqrt{\frac{m}{kg^3} \cdot \frac{s^2 kg}{m^3}} = \frac{s}{m} \sqrt{\frac{s^2}{kg^2 m^2}} = \frac{s}{m} \cdot \frac{s}{kg \cdot m} = \frac{1}{kg} \cdot \frac{s^2}{m^2}$$

$$\frac{1}{C} = kg \frac{m^2}{s^2} = \frac{1}{2} m v^2 = \text{energy}$$

$$hC = (6.62607E - 34)(1.55976565E33) = 1.03351 \text{seconds} \approx 1.0 \text{seconds}$$

$$hC = \left(kg \frac{m}{s^2} \cdot m \cdot s \right) \left(\frac{1}{kg} \cdot \frac{s^2}{m^2} \right)$$

$$= \left(kg \frac{m^2}{s} \right) \left(\frac{1}{kg} \cdot \frac{s^2}{m^2} \right) = \text{seconds}$$

$$KE_{earth} = \frac{1}{2} (5.972E24 kg) (30,290 m/s)^2 = 2.7396E33 J$$

$$\hbar_{\odot} = (hC) KE_{earth} = (1.03351s)(2.7396E33J) = 2.8314E33 J \cdot s$$

Returning To Angular Momentum, Quantum Gravity, And Ancient Megalithic Sites

The outer circle of the ancient stone observatory, Stonehenge, is 110 meters in diameter. If the velocity of the Earth at its equatorial surface is

$$24. \quad v_{rot} = \frac{L_{earth}}{M_e R_e} \cdot \frac{60}{24} = 464.5975 m/s$$

Then, at Stonehenge it is

$$25. \quad v_{rot} = (465 m/s) \cos(51^\circ) = 292.38 m/s$$

since Stonehenge is at a latitude of 51 degrees. This is the velocity at which the stones at Stonehenge move with the rotation of the Earth that determines the position of the Sun in the sky. Divide this by the 110 meter diameter of Stonehenge and we have

$$26. \quad \frac{292.38 m/s}{110m} (1 \text{second}) = 2.65 \approx 2.5$$

is the number of megalithic yards recurrent throughout Stonehenge. The ancients could have measured the second with their heart beat, which is about 1 second. And a pendulum, with length of one megalithic yard does one swing in about a second.

The Planck constant \hbar has units of angular momentum ($Joule \cdot s = kg \cdot m^2/s$) and in quantum mechanics the orbital angular momentum is $L = mvr = n\hbar$ where n is the orbital number, meaning it is

quantized in terms of integer multiples of \hbar and fundamental particles have spin, like that of an electron is $(1/2)\hbar$ which means that angular momentum is fundamental to quantum structure just as gravity is fundamental to spacetime. At the Planck length $l_p = \sqrt{\hbar G/c^3}$, quantum gravity effects dominate, since this is described in terms of \hbar of angular momentum in quantum mechanics, G of gravity, and c of relativity we say at this length spacetime may have a granular, quantized structure, so it follows spin networks could define spacetime geometry for a unified field theory. This one is called Loop Quantum Gravity. If spacetime has a moment of inertia it is said that

$$I_{spacetime} \sim \hbar/\omega_{Planck}$$

Where

$$\omega_{Planck} \sim c^5/\hbar^5 G$$

is the the Planck frequency. No complete theory yet reconciles general relativity with quantum mechanics but the r^2 duality is a hint. Experiments like GINGER are aiming to test this but it is thought angular momentum is the missing link between quantum mechanics and gravity. I think from my wave solution we may be able to find what I found about the Solar System (governed by gravity), like

$$\frac{\hbar_{\odot}^2}{GM_m^3} \cdot \frac{1}{c} = 1second$$

$$\hbar_{\odot} = (1second)KE_e$$

might tell us something about quanta, like the atom's proton in

$$\left(\frac{1}{6\alpha^2} \sqrt{\frac{4\pi\hbar}{Gc}} \right) \cdot \frac{r_p}{m_p} = 1second$$

$$\left(\sqrt{\phi \cdot \frac{\pi r_p}{\alpha^4 G m_p^3}} \right) \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{h}{c} = 1second$$

It may be that this is an abstract problem that exists in both the problems between quantum mechanics and gravity and the problems between stone alignments in ancient observatories such as at Stonehenge and that our ancient ancestors solved with the 2.5 megalithic yards. I say this because we found in this paper that

$$v_{rot} = \frac{L_{earth}}{M_e R_e} \cdot \frac{60}{24}$$

$$\frac{L_{earth}}{\hbar_{\odot}} 24 = 60 \quad \text{Where}$$

$$\frac{60}{24} = 2.5$$

The Author

